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Transnational Access to radio frequency testing facilities

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ABSTRACT

The transnational access facilities HNOSS and Xbox both fulfilled their engagements by giving a total of 4,494 and 10,701 hours of access respectively.

ARIES Consortium, 2022

For more information on ARIES, its partners and contributors please see <http://aries.web.cern.ch>

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	Name	Partner	Date
Authored by	Roger Ruber	CERN	01/05/2022
Edited by	Sabrina El Yacoubi	CERN	20/05/2022
Reviewed by	Maurizio Vretenar	CERN	20/06/2022
Approved by	Maurizio Vretenar [Scientific coordinator] Steering Committee		30/06/2022

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. DESCRIPTION OF INFRASTRUCTURE.....4

1.1 HNOSS4

1.2 XBOX.....4

1.3 DESCRIPTION OF THE SELECTION PROCEDURE5

2. SUMMARY OF TA PROVIDED5

3. HIGHLIGHTS OF TA RESULTS6

4. LIST OF TA PROJECT9

5. LIST OF TA PUBLICATIONS..... 10

Executive summary

The Trans-National Access (TNA) program on Radio Frequency (RF) Testing alleviates the use of complex research facilities which researchers typically do not have access to at their home institute. This in turn enables the facilities to perform novel experiments and expand collaborative research across Europe and worldwide. The two TNA facilities HNOSS and Xbox included in this work package are located at Uppsala University, Sweden, and CERN, Switzerland. They focus respectively on superconducting radio frequency cavities and normal conducting radio frequency cavities.

1. Description of infrastructure

1.1 HNOSS

HNOSS is a versatile cryostat system for testing superconducting radio-frequency (SRF) accelerating and deflecting cavities located at Uppsala University, Sweden. The facility comprises two cryostats and a test bunker with cryogenic feed box for short cryomodules. It can be used for low and high-power testing of up to two cavities simultaneously and can thereby be used to study cross-talk between devices. It is equipped with three high-power radio-frequency (RF) stations providing up to 400 kW/3.5 ms pulsed or 40 kW/CW.

The facility is operated by an experienced and well-trained team in superconducting cavities and cryogenics. It assists users all the way from installation to test and analysis of the performance data.

1.2 XBOX

The Xboxes are klystron-based X band test stands located at CERN in Geneva, Switzerland. The test stands are dedicated to the testing and development of high-gradient normal conducting RF accelerating structures and high-power RF components. At present there are three Xboxes: two with each powered by a 50 MW/1.5 μ s/50 Hz klystron and the third is powered by four 6 MW/5 μ s/400 Hz klystrons combined in pairs.

The Xboxes were constructed and are being used to high-power test the main linac accelerating structures and novel RF components for the Compact Linear Collider (CLIC). The test stands are just as useful for developing high gradient and power structures for X-band FELs, Compton/Thomson sources and as potential test units of RF units used in high-performance compact linacs.

Access to the Xboxes is granted in two modes: Primary access is given to accelerating structures and RF components powered by RF directly, and parasitic access is given to experiments dedicated to projects such as high gradient research and diagnostic developments.

1.3 DESCRIPTION OF THE SELECTION PROCEDURE

WP12 has a common User Selection Panel (USP) for the two tasks 12.1 and 12.2. All the Panel has expertise in RF with a mixture of specializations to cover the superconducting HNOSS and normal-conducting Xboxes. The criteria for choosing the members of the User Selection Panel were that they should be from among the worldwide RF community with one member from the Americas, Asia, and Europe each. In addition, they should represent one member each from superconducting RF, normal conducting RF, and RF manufacturing technologies. The final panel consists of Jiaru Shi (Tsinghua University, China), Vyacheslav Yakovlev (Fermi National Laboratory, USA), Kenneth Österberg (Helsinki University, Finland), and the two work package leaders Walter Wuensch (CERN, Switzerland) and Roger Ruber (Uppsala University, Sweden).

2. Summary of TA provided

The initial engagements were 2,880 and 6,000 access units respectively for the HNOSS and Xbox facilities, with 4 projects for each. This engagement was reviewed after the Covid-19 pandemic started which, as in many other institutes, limited the access to research facilities. For our TA facilities there was no impact on the amount of access units, which exceeded the engagements. But the pandemic unfortunately caused that one already approved project was not carried out. This was due to coronavirus restrictions followed by the departure from the proposing university of key staff. The access provided by the facilities is summarised in Table 1.

Table 1: Number of projects, users, and access units for the TA facilities.

Facility	No. of actual projects	Total no. of projects Annex 1*	No. of actual users	Total no. of users Annex 1	No. of actual access units	Total no. of access units Annex 1*
HNOSS	4	4	49	44	4,494	3,790
XBox	4	4	30	24	10,701	7,500

*) Updated according the 2020 amendment.

The total amount of users in this work package was 68, of which 8 (11%) was female. They originated from 6 different countries with the distribution shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: Distribution of users per country, listed in alphabetic order.

3. Highlights of TA results

Overall the projects executed have seen a very satisfied users base. The projects have been complex to install and operate and for some projects additional equipment had to be borrowed from partners to execute the project successfully.

The first project at the XBox facility was a parasitic experiment by a group from Uppsala University led by Marek Jacewicz. The team developed instrumentation called **Uppsala/CLIC X-band Spectrometer** to study dark and breakdown currents. The experiment was installed in Xbox-1 and the in-situ system provided complementary data on high-gradient effects. The investigations proceeded with GEANT4 simulations and experimental measurements at CERN. We found that there is very little change in the pulse-to-pulse characteristics of the dark current, even in the time scale of minutes, unless a breakdown occurred inside the structure. The resulting energy distribution of emitted electrons is therefore broad and continuous to the limit given by the accelerating gradient present in the structure. The breakdown events often reset the emitting sites which we observe by measuring changes in the energy spectra. With more sensitive setup these could be used to pinpoint the location of the new emitters and perhaps predict the location of the next breakdown. Study of the dark current behaviour in function of surface field shows a very good agreement with underline theory of field emission however requires much higher values of the enhancement factor β to scale the data. This again confirms that the observed current is a superposition of the currents emanating from multiple emission sites.

The first project at the HNOSS facility was the test of a **high-beta elliptical cavity** designed and constructed by CEA Saclay, France, in a team led by Frank Peauger. The cavity was transported to Uppsala with the vacuum part of the fundamental mode power coupler already installed. The air side

doorknob was installed by the CEA team in Uppsala. The required high-power RF system was borrowed from ESS, Sweden. Cavity and coupler were first conditioned at room temperature, then cooled down to 2 K. A maximum accelerating gradient of 16 MV/m was reached with an incident RF power of 290 kW. The effect of Lorenz force detuning was visible at high field, with a variation of the field amplitude on the flat top of the pulse. A second cool down and test was performed with a modified connection to the frequency tuner driver. After the modification, the fast piezo driven tuner proved to be effective in counter-working the effects of Lorenz force detuning.

The second project at the XBox facility was a high-power test of a **new barrel open cavity X-band RF pulse compressor** designed and built by PSI, Switzerland, along with a **novel multiple cavity correction cavity chain** designed and built by Tsinghua University, China. The latter forms near-flat pulses from the exponentially decaying pulse from a SLED-type pulse compressor. Together, the pair forms a very compact alternative to a SLED2-type pulse compressor for use in multi-bunch linacs. These two devices were installed in Xbox2 and were successfully operated together. Users from Tsinghua University and PSI actively participated in the test through activities such as installation, operation of the XBoxes, establishing dedicated tests to verify behaviour, carrying out the tests and collecting data and analysing results. Through this work it has been verified that the corrector cavity and pulse compressor systems behaved according to expectation from calculations. They have been pushed to output powers in excess of 50 MW without significant high-power activity, limited only by other parts of the Xbox system.

The second project at the HNOSS facility was proposed by IPN Orsay, France, for a high-power test of a cryostat-module (cryomodule) with two double-spoke cavities fully equipped with fundamental power coupler and frequency tuner. This cryomodule, designed and developed by the team from IPN Orsay, is a prototype for the high-power proton accelerator for the ESS project. The goal is to validate the design by performing a full RF conditioning, operation at nominal power, and tuning the cavities to nominal frequency.

The third project at HNOSS, proposed by the Technical University Lodz, Poland, made use of the cryomodule and frequency tuning system of the second project. Its objectives **were tests and verification of electronics developed for the control of SRF cavity resonance frequency by means of a fast tuner based on piezo-electric activator elements**. Thanks to the project the TUL team was able to verify requirements for designed piezo driver. During this study the last confirmation of the hardware operation parameters have been planned – before scheduled mass production process. Thanks to the verification with the spoke cavity cryomodule infrastructure it has been revealed that main parameters of designed driver has to be modified in respect to the already agreed one. The project triggered a discussion between different stakeholders of ESS cryomodules which resulted in the revision and modification of the frequency tuning controls. The project thereby avoided the risk of mass production of piezo driver systems which would be not compliant with the real requirements for the ESS cryomodules.

The third project at the XBox facility consisted in the high-power test of two transverse deflecting cavities; one is a so-called **crab cavity designed for the CLIC final focus system** and the other is the **deflector for a system to measure longitudinal profiles of very short bunches in XFELs**. The

former is a 13 cell structure built by University of Lancaster, UK, and the second a 20 cell structure built by SSRF, China. The two structures were high field conditioned and long-term operated in two slots in XBox-3 with input powers up to 40 MW. Due to coronavirus restrictions all of the user participation was remote.

The fourth project at HNOSS, proposed by a team from CERN, was the **test and validation of a superconducting crab-cavity for the HL-LHC**. The test was dedicated to a prototype double-quarter wave crab cavity originally fabricated by Niowave, USA, first tested at JLab, USA, and then by CERN. The goal was to compare the test results by different institutions and to validate the performance of the prototype cavity. Due to the Coronavirus pandemic, the project was performed by the local team with remote assistance by the team from CERN. The vacuum, cryogenic, and RF systems were commissioned. The ambient magnetic field was compensated by external coils during cavity cooling down. The performance of the crab-cavity was confirmed according the specifications.

The fourth project at the XBox facility was proposed by a team from the Eindhoven University of Technology, the Netherlands. Its objective was the **measurement of average power limitation for high gradient X-band accelerating structures for future light sources**, operating at higher repetition rates than their predecessors. It aimed for a better understanding of the average power capabilities of high gradient accelerating structures and their limitations by peak surface electric field and cooling capacity. The project was approved but was unfortunately not carried out due to coronavirus restrictions followed by the departure from the proposing university of key staff.

4. List of TA project

Project Acronym	Project Title	Access Units
ARIES-FREIA-HNOSS-2017-01	ESS high-beta elliptical cavity	1,330
ARIES-FREIA-HNOSS-2018-01	Validation of prototype double-spoke cavity cryomodule	2,048
ARIES-FREIA-HNOSS-2019-01	RF and piezo actuators study on spoke cavities	36
ARIES-FREIA-HNOSS-2020-01	HL-LHC crab cavity cold testing	1,080
ARIES-CERN-XBox-2017-01	Dark and breakdown currents studies with Uppsala/CLIC X-band Spectrometer	1,680
ARIES-CERN-XBox-2018-01	X-band pulse compression chain	4,000
ARIES-CERN-XBox-2019-01	X-band RF deflecting structure testing	5,021
ARIES-CERN-XBox-2020-01	Measurement of the Average Power Limitation for High Gradient X-band Accelerating Structures for Future Light Sources	0

5. List of TA publications

TA Project Acronym	Publication Year	Authors	Title	References	Publication type	Peer reviewed	DOI	Open Access
ARIES-FREIA-HNOSS-2017-01	2018	H. Li <i>et al.</i>	First High-Power Test of the ESS High Beta Elliptical Cavity at FREIA	Proceedings of LINAC2018, Beijing, China, Proton and Ion Accelerators and Applications	conference paper	No	Yes	Yes
ARIES-FREIA-HNOSS-2017-01	2018	R. Santiago Kern <i>et al.</i>	Cryogenic Synopsis from the Testing of the Fully Equipped ESS' High β Cavity ESS086-P01 (Part I)	Uppsala University internal report FREIA Report 2018/04	Report	no	http://urn.kb.se/resolve?urn=urn:nbn:se:uu:diva-365758	yes
ARIES-FREIA-HNOSS-2017-01	2018	R. Santiago Kern <i>et al.</i>	Cryogenic Synopsis from the Testing of the Fully Equipped ESS' High β Cavity ESS086-P01 (Part II)	Uppsala University internal report FREIA Report 2018/06	Report	no	http://urn.kb.se/resolve?urn=urn:nbn:se:uu:diva-365761	yes
ARIES-FREIA-	2019	H. Li <i>et al.</i>	The Integration and RF Conditioning of the ESS	IPAC 2019	Conference proceedings	no	10.18429/JA CoW-	yes

HNOSS-2018-01			Double-Spoke Prototype Cryomodule at FREIA				IPAC2019-WEPRB061	
ARIES-FREIA-HNOSS-2018-01	2019	A. Miyazaki et al.	Conditioning Experience of the ESS Spoke Cryomodule	19th International Conference on RF Superconductivity (SRF 2019)	Conference proceedings	no	10.18429/JA CoW-SRF2019-THP058	yes
ARIES-FREIA-HNOSS-2018-01	2019	R. Santiago Kern et al.	RF Performance of the spoke prototype cryomodule for ESS	Uppsala University internal report FREIA Report 2019/05	Report	no	N/A	yes
ARIES-FREIA-HNOSS-2018-01	2019	H. Li et al.	Cryogenic Performance of the spoke prototype cryomodule for ESS	Uppsala University internal report FREIA Report 2019/08	Report	no	N/A	yes
ARIES-FREIA-HNOSS-2020-01	2020	A. Miyazaki et al.	First cold test of a crab cavity at the GERSEMI cryostat for the HL-LHC project	arXiv	Journal Publication	No	https://arxiv.org/abs/2011.05210	Yes
ARIES-FREIA-HNOSS-2020-01	2021	R. Ruber et al.	Accelerator Development at the FREIA Laboratory	arXiv	Journal Publication	No	https://arxiv.org/abs/2103.05265	Yes

ARIES-CERN-XBox-2017-01	2019	M. Jacewicz	Dark currents studies with the Uppsala X-band spectrometer at XBox test stand at CERN	Accelerator Physics and Instrumentation	Report (Other academic)	No	http://urn.kb.se/resolve?urn=urn:nbn:se:uu:diva-392193	Yes
ARIES-CERN-XBox-2018-01	2019	Yuliang Jiang, Hao Zha, Ping Wang, Jiaru Shi, Huaibi Chen, William L Millar, and Igor Syrathev	Demonstration of a cavity-based pulse compression system for pulse shape correction	Phys. Rev. Accel. Beams 22, 082001	Journal publication	Yes	https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevAccelBeams.22.082001	Yes
ARIES-CERN-XBox-2018-01	2020	P. Craievich et al.	Novel X-band transverse deflection structure with variable polarization	Phys. Rev. Accel. Beams 23, 112001	Journal publication	Yes	https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevAccelBeams.23.112001	Yes